

INSIGHTS OF AMAZONIAN BIOMASS BURNING SOURCES USING BIOMARKERS IN THE ANDES CORDILLERA REGION

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RESUMEN. Este estudio investiga el potencial de los biomarcadores (levoglucosano y galactosano) como indicadores indirectos de la actividad de los incendios forestales en la Amazonia y Bolivia, utilizando muestras obtenidas en la estación Chacaltaya Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW), situada en la región de los Andes Tropicales. Los análisis preliminares exploran las asociaciones entre estos biomarcadores y los datos de incendios forestales del Instituto Brasileño de Investigaciones Espaciales (INPE) durante la fase de transición de seco a húmedo (septiembre a noviembre). Se utilizan dos enfoques analíticos: uno incluye todas las muestras de materia particulada (PM), incluidas las afectadas por El Niño-Oscilación del Sur (ENOS), mientras que el otro excluye las muestras afectadas por ENOS. Los resultados indican que, en años normales, sin eventos ENSO, el biomarcador galactosano se asocia favorablemente con las llamas bolivianas y negativamente con los incendios forestales amazónicos. El levoglucosano, en cambio, parece tener una relación más compleja con los incendios forestales amazónicos. Se justifican nuevas investigaciones exhaustivas para mejorar la comprensión de las fuentes de quema de biomasa registradas en los glaciares de los Andes Tropicales y refinar la interpretación de estos registros de biomarcadores.

Palabras-clave: Incendios Florestales; Biomarcadores; Glaciares tropicales

RESUMO. Este estudo investiga o potencial de biomarcadores (levoglucosano e galactosano) como proxies para a atividade de incêndios florestais na Amazônia e na Bolívia, utilizando amostras obtidas da estação Chacaltaya Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) situada na região dos Andes Tropicais. Análises preliminares exploram as associações entre esses biomarcadores e os dados de queimadas do Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais (INPE) durante a fase de transição seca para úmida (setembro a novembro). Duas abordagens analíticas são utilizadas: uma inclui todas as amostras de material particulado (PM), incluindo aquelas afetadas pelo El Niño-Oscilação Sul (ENSO), enquanto a outra exclui as amostras afetadas pelo ENSO. Os resultados indicam que, em anos normais, sem eventos ENSO, o biomarcador galactosano está favoravelmente associado às chamas bolivianas e negativamente associado aos incêndios florestais na Amazônia. O levoglucosano, por outro lado, parece ter uma relação mais complexa com os incêndios florestais na Amazônia. São necessárias mais investigações abrangentes para melhorar a compreensão das fontes de queima de biomassa registradas nos glaciares dos Andes Tropicais e aperfeiçoar a interpretação destes registros de biomarcadores.

Palavras-chave: Incêndio Florestal; Biomarcadores; Geleiras Tropicais

ABSTRACT. This study investigates the potential of biomarkers (levoglucosan and galactosan) as proxies for wildfire activity in the Amazon and Bolivia, utilizing samples obtained from the Chacaltaya Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) station situated in the Tropical Andes region. Preliminary analyses explore the associations between these biomarkers and wildfire data from the Brazilian Institute of Space Research (INPE) during the dry-to-wet transition phase (September to November). Two analytical approaches are used: one includes all particulate matter (PM) samples, including those impacted by the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), while the other excludes ENSO-affected samples. The findings indicate that in normal years, without ENSO events, the galactosan biomarker is favorably associated with Bolivian flames and negatively associated with Amazon wildfires. Levoglucosan, on the other hand, appears to have a more complex relationship with Amazon wildfires. Further comprehensive investigations are warranted to enhance the understanding of biomass burning sources recorded in Tropical Andes glaciers and refine the interpretation of these biomarker records.

Keywords: Wildfires; Biomarkers; Tropical Glaciers

1. INTRODUCTION

Glaciers are an important component of the Earth's surface as they cover around 10 % of it (Winkler et al., 2010). The mountain glaciers (0.5 %) are mainly located in the Arctic, in the Alps, in the Himalayas and Central Asia, in the Andes, in Western North America and in Austral islands. Glaciers act as excellent indicators of climate variations as they usually expand (retreat) during cold (warm) periods (Veetil et al., 2017).

In the tropics, glaciers exist in South America (from Bolivia to Venezuela), Africa (Kilimanjaro, Mount Kenya and Rwenzori) and Oceania (West Papua). The Andes have approximately 99% of the ice masses located in the tropics (Kaser, 1999). South American glaciers are distributed predominantly from 12°N to 23°S within 70% of ice cover in Peru, 20% in Bolivia and 10% in Ecuador, Colombia and Venezuela. In the central Andes, the precipitation is regulated, mainly, by winds coming from the east, which originates on the Atlantic Ocean and mixes to the air masses of the Amazonian origin (da Rocha Ribeiro et al., 2018). The Central Andean glaciers (Peru and Bolivia) are characterized by a wet and a dry season and signals of these changes in the Amazon atmosphere (e.g., pollutants such as black carbon due to biomass burning and trace elements) are recorded (Correia et al., 2003).

Large-scale deforestation and biomass burning in the Amazon Basin are direct consequences of economic practices and human occupation. Brazil and Bolivia are the two countries most affected, accounting for 70% and 10% of fire event observations, respectively (Magalhães et al., 2019). Wildfires can emit a wide range of chemical compounds to the atmosphere. They are then transported by atmospheric circulation and can be deposited at the snow surface where they will be archived and later extracted by ice-core drilling (Osmont et al., 2019).

Biomarkers are quantifiable signals of a biological state or situation. Levoglucosan, Galactosan, and Mannitol are biomarkers that offer information on different aspects of the environment and health. Levoglucosan serves as a chemical indicator of biomass burning, like that from forest fires or burning wood in homes. Galactosan is a different marker for biomass burning, frequently linked to the burning of hardwood. Mannitol is a biomarker that can show if there are fungal spores in the air, which is important for studying air quality and respiratory health (Li et al., 2018; Salma et al., 2017).

1.2. STUDY AREA

The Chacaltaya Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) station (lat. -16.350500° , long. -68.131389° , 5240 m a.s.l.) is currently the highest site in the GAW network. It is located some 1400 m above the Altiplano high plateau (mean elevation of about 3750 m a.s.l.), bordered to the west by the Cordillera Occidental. Mt. Chacaltaya lies within the northern segment of the Cordillera Real and is located about 40 km from the nearest part of the lake Titicaca and about 15km north of the La Paz–El Alto conurbation. El Alto (La Paz) is a fast-growing city, with its population having increased from approximately 60 000 to 921 000 inhabitants during 1976–2012.

General atmospheric circulation shows an annual cycle of dry and wet seasons, typical of the tropical zone (Espinoza et al., 2020). At Chacaltaya station (Figure 1), the average atmospheric pressure is 534 hPa, which is about half of the value at sea level; the temperature average is around 0 °C, and annual precipitation (mostly solid) is 865 mm in water equivalent depth (Perry et al., 2017). Four seasons are defined for this region based on the circulation and precipitation changes: (1) the wet season from December to March (65–70 % of the annual precipitation); (2) the wet-to-dry transition season in April; (3) the dry season from May to August, and (4) the dry-to-wet transition season from September to November (SON) used to mark the onset of the rainy season that has become quite dry over the last decades (Espinoza et al., 2019). In the dry and dry-to-wet seasons, winds with a westerly component blow over the Altiplano towards the station, bringing mineral dust to Chacaltaya station along with biomass burning tracers (Chauvigné et al., 2019). Biomass burning emissions are transported to the Altiplano through the valleys located in the east of the Cordillera Real (Bourgeois et al., 2015; Magalhães et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Chacaltaya glacier located at Tropical Andes.

2. MATERIALS

In this work, we explored the set of samples analysis were achieved using a High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) with pulsed amperometric detection. This arrangements was applied for the analytical process of a recent study (Moreno et al., 2024) that provided the

biomarkers results for this work . We explored the results from anhydrous saccharides detected (levoglucosan and its stereoisomer galactosan), polyols (arabitol, sorbitol, mannitol), and glucose to evaluate the concentration variability linked to wildfires levels from Amazon and Bolivia. The wildfires database was obtained from the Brazilian Institute of Space Research – INPE.

3. RESULTS

The preliminary results present the associations between two biomarkers analyzed. We explored the levoglucosan and galactosan levels by two distinct arrangements. First, we explored the set of all four particulate matter (PM) samples correspondent to period (PM10 - SON from 2012; PM2.5 mean – SON from 2013 to 2015; PM10 from 2016 and PM10 from 2019) and their associations (red, Figure 2) with Amazon biome and Bolivian wildfires from INPE (Instituto Nacional de Pesquisa) data for each period of dry-to-wet transition months (SON). Secondly, we explored three of four sets of samples, discarding the samples correspondent to El-Niño event, to evaluate the association with the same wildfires periods (blue, Figure 2). Our findings indicate that in the second case the galactosan biomarker is well associated to Bolivian (positively) and Amazon (negatively) wildfires records. Also, the levoglucosan present a subtle association to the Amazon wildfires.

Figure 2. The associations of Amazon and Bolivian wildfires records versus biomarkers Levoglucosan (a) and (c) and Galactosan (b) and (d).

4. CONCLUSION

Our exploratory analysis shows that during the regular years (without ENSO events) the biomarkers (mainly galactosan) is suggested to provide the wildfire variability record by remote sensing analysis. Our results presents a new perspective to better understanding the biomass

sources recorded at Tropical Andes glaciers and further analysis still need to deep investigation on this theme.

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